

THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract. *The 21st century is an information age as well as digital technologies age. The rapid development of information technology provides us with advanced teaching means—multimedia. It is true that multimedia has many advantages in English teaching, such as offering more information, saving more time, stimulating students' imagination and creativity, and so on. Although multimedia has many advantages, some scholars suggested that it should not be used blindly. What we should know is that multimedia just only plays an assisting role in English teaching. The thesis found out the opinion of primary school teachers of Uzbekistan how useful the multimedia application is for teaching young learners and developing their speaking skills in the classroom, if it is an effective tool for self-education and self-assessment.*

Keywords: *multimedia, assisting role, application*

At present, much attention is paid to the use of multimedia in teaching foreign languages, especially to young learners, in accordance with the specifics of their age and special ability to perceive educational material. Pedagogical systems and educational technologies, in particular multimedia, attract great attention of teachers as well in order to improve the education of young learners. Many scientists in their studies consider the use of different types of multimedia, both collectively and separately. In their studies, some scientists use the definition of “multimedia application”, “multimedia training resource”, “multimedia technologies”, “multimedia electronic manual to teaching materials” or “computer (multimedia) program”. Let us consider the concepts of “teaching materials” and “multimedia application to the textbook” adopted in the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan: “The set of teaching materials, according to modern requirements for educational sets, includes a Pupil’s textbook, a Workbook, a Teacher’s Manual, and a Multimedia Application to this textbook. CMD is being developed “in accordance with the state educational standard, curriculum and program and meeting didactic, methodological, pedagogical, as well as psychological, aesthetic and hygienic requirements.

Multimedia instruction refers to learning environments that contain both words and pictures with the intention to promote learning, such as illustrated textbooks, narrated slideshow presentations, online narrated animations, and educational computer games.

Text and graphics include slideshows, presentations, diagrams and infographics. Audio includes podcasts and recordings. Screen captures, lecture captures and animation are examples of video components of multimedia. Other multimedia components include blogs, vlogs, webinars and other interactive content.

Multimedia approach aims at providing meaningful learning experience via a mix of media in order to achieve predetermined objectives. Multimedia approach provides the opportunity to gain mastery of competencies and skills.

The rapid development of information technology provides us with advanced teaching means—multimedia. It is true that multimedia has many advantages in English teaching, such as offering more information, saving more time, stimulating students' imagination and creativity, and so on. Multimedia content helps to vary and enhance the learning process, and leads to

better knowledge retention. Educational video can provide more opportunities for students to engage with the content. Students around the world can learn from course content made available through video.

Many studies have shown that many students are tired of traditional English classes, and are interested in new style learning. They have positive attitude towards computer technology used in the classroom, and such technology does have a positive impact, because multimedia teaching have many advantages over other media in English teaching.

There are some advantages of using multimedia in the classroom:

Arousing the students’ interest. Famous scientist Albert Einstein had a famous saying: “Interest is the best teacher”. So the interest has always been seen as the best helper to learn the knowledge. The traditional teaching method is that teachers talk from the beginning to the end with a chalk and a mouth. Such teaching is very single, which makes students lose interest, until weariness. Leo Tolstoy said: “The successful teaching is not to force, but rather to stimulate student’s desire” [3]. In other words, if student have no interest or desire on teaching subject, then, even if the teacher talk how carefully, the results are fruitlessly. Therefore, teachers should try their best to get students to become interest in one topic of knowledge point, and make the students with a strong passion and enthusiasm to participate in teaching. Multimedia is this kind of media which can show a variety of sounds, images, animation, and other effects, firmly grasping the student’s interest. It also can stimulate the students’ strong desire to study English actively. Multi-media teaching can not only greatly stimulate students’ interest in learning, but also make teaching becomes vivid and lively.

Improving students’ self-learning ability. The purpose of teaching in the classroom is not only to impart knowledge to students. The most important thing is teaching students how to learn and making students change from “want me to study” to “I want to learn” in thinking, from passive learning to active learning. Therefore, students are free from the passive learning environment, take initiative at learning, and develop their own self-learning good habits gradually. It also can enable students to tap into a good way of learning English independently, keep the cultivation of motivation and interest in learning English so as to make students really love the English, really free from the passive learning environment in English learning. The use of multimedia will be conducive to transition for students from the traditional passive learning to active state for independent study. For example, teachers can select the appropriate E-work arrangements to the students from the multimedia courseware after class, so that they can complete the relevant extra-curricular work, and send message to the teacher through their own e-mails, the teacher via electronic E-mail marking responses to student. In this way, students can not only see their learning outcomes in the shortest period of time, but also continue stimulating interest in their own learning through the multimedia network.

Improving students’ innovative ability. Meanwhile, multi-media teaching can also develop student’s ability to innovate. Things need to innovate, Einstein said: “Imagination is more important than knowledge, and is a source of knowledge”. In teaching, the teachers should pay attention to tap the imagination of students. To use multimedia can achieve the desired results and find unlimited resources in textbooks.

Cultivating students’ communication skills. Uzbek students learning English often lack a certain language environment and opportunities for practicing language, but the actual language teaching is often to focus only on words and sentence structures of learning, ignoring

its specific application. Thus, many students get a fixed, isolated knowledge points from textbooks, but the ability of using these knowledge points to the real life of the capacity is relatively poor. When encountering with the reality of different occasions, they will be helpless. Through multi-media teaching, we can create real-life scenes in the classroom. It is not only to shorten the distance between teaching and practice and give students the opportunity to use English to communicate, but also to satisfy their curiosity in psychology and stimulate the expression of desire.

Increasing classroom capacity. With only a tiny mouse, teachers can avoid using of multiple exchange of tape recorders, video recorders, overhead projectors, etc., greatly increase the output of information, speed up the pace of the classroom, increase the density of the classroom, and save a lot of time which teachers spend on writing on the blackboard. Multi-media teaching rhythm is adapted to the needs of modernization to meet the student's desire for knowledge. It can expand text-related materials. The use of multimedia technologies can make students notice a clear knowledge and a new expansion by huge information capacity which shows by all kinds of media.

Strategies for Using Multimedia

Combining Modern Teaching Methods With Traditional Teaching Methods

There is no doubt that modern teaching methods have many advantages over traditional ones. Compared to traditional textbook or workbook, a multimedia program can provide immediate feedback on the correctness of the learner's response. Nevertheless, traditional teaching methods are still commonly used because of their own strong points. So teachers should combine their strong points with modern teaching methods, which not only raise classroom teaching quality and efficiency, but also improve teaching and learning environment between teachers and students.

Viewing Multimedia as the Assistance to Teaching

Multimedia features including sound, animation, video, and record allow computers as model skills to help students and teachers assess them. The option to provide guidance only when needed makes it possible for computers to support learning flexibly. Multimedia enables students to manipulate and create material to learn by doing. But when we use computers in the teaching, we should understand they can only assist but cannot take place of all the other teaching methods. It is wrong for the teachers to take no notice of textbooks when they are designing courseware. Now that multimedia can only help English teaching, teachers should get a clear idea of how and when to make good use of them. Application of multimedia technology aims to improve teaching, but teaching is not intended for multimedia. There is no doubt that teaching needs multimedia, but using multimedia does not mean enhancing teaching efficiency. For example, if the teaching can be completed in a few minutes in an ordinary classroom, it is certainly unnecessary to use multimedia. Because of all kinds of media in multimedia technology, sometimes students may concentrate not on teaching contents but on media. If so, students are not able to grasp teaching contents well. That means not every class need multimedia teaching. One important principle is: When simple is best, keep it simple. Therefore, multimedia can only be used as a supplement to classroom English teaching.

Building the Ideal Relationship Between Teachers and Students

Application of modern teaching methods can make teaching efficient and do part of work instead of teachers. But it is wrong for some people to hold the view that machine can take place

of human beings. It is more challenging role for teachers now that the expectations are more complex. In other words, in the information age, the role of teachers has evolved, moving from a traditional teaching role (being the “holder” of knowledge) to being “facilitators” (helping students learning the way each learns best) when learners take advantages of the true potential of multimedia as learning tools. At any time teachers’ explanation plays an extreme part, which is a language art and cannot be substituted by any teaching methods. Although teaching methods have changed, teaching laws and characteristics of students’ development in body and mind remain unchanged. Teachers should play a leading role in the teaching. In the past, students were thought of to be passive knowledge receiver.

However, the role of students with learning has changed in the information age. There is a movement towards learner-centered approaches. Thus, students became learning subjects. How actively students participate in the learning situation is an important parameter for the learning environment. One part of the role of students is to actively formulate their own goals for their learning goals. For another thing, students should take a role as a teacher. Being a teacher is beneficial to improve one’s own understanding.

Strengthening Teacher Training

Multimedia assisted English teaching requires teachers with multimedia computer operating experience. It is a challenge for teachers using multimedia because of heavy preparation work and increasing workload. In the light of the problems the teachers should be trained with the use of modern equipments. They should be familiar with the operation. They should be expert in one thing and good at many. They should know well about modern educational theories and techniques.

The Principles of Multimedia-Assisted Teaching

- (1) Scientific principles. Namely, courseware design cannot appear any errors;
- (2) Subsidiary principle. We must always adhere to: Although multi-media teaching has many advantages, it is only a supplementary means, and does not substitute for the role of people;
- (3) Interactivity principle. More interactivity between teachers and students, students and multimedia, more effective results we will have;
- (4) Combination principle. Combine the advantages of modern teaching and the traditional teaching organically

Summing up the article, I can say that teachers actively use the multimedia application in the classroom. According to English teachers’ opinion, all the activities given in the multimedia apps are very effective to use in English classes for young learners, but the best way to use them is for introducing a new vocabulary in the lesson, for video instructions to avoid using the native language (L1) when explaining the task (on the principle of “better to see once”), for listening to songs and watching cartoons.

The multimedia applications to the textbook sets stimulate interest in the English language, increase the motivation for learning, as when correctly performing interactive activities, young learners can hear words of approval and praise (Good job; Well done!). In case of failure, they also feel support (Try again, please).

Taking into account the solution of the problem of using multimedia in the process of teaching in elementary school, and the preparation of teachers and students of elementary school

for the process of multimedia learning, we have identified the didactic conditions for the use of multimedia technologies in the process of teaching younger students:

1. the inclusion of multimedia technologies in a holistic learning process - in the study of all academic disciplines of elementary school;
2. application in the classroom of subject-oriented program-methodological complex, taking into account the content and logic of studying the subject;
3. the use of multimedia programs that correspond to the didactic purpose of the lesson, organically included in its structure and leading to a rational solution of the tasks set;
4. Conducting classes using multimedia learning software should be carried out by a primary school teacher who has a sufficient level of knowledge and skills to carry out this work;
5. creation in the classroom of an atmosphere conducive to the formation of positive motives for the use of MMT in cognitive activity among younger students;
6. the use in the classroom of multimedia teaching software that is technologically and operationally accessible to younger students and more effective than other teaching aids used in the classroom.

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